

Impact of 1940s redlining on self-rated health and mortality among older adults

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Abstract

Background

Areas “redlined” by the Home Owners’ Loan Corporation (HOLC) in the 1930s against Black neighborhoods are associated with worse present day area health outcomes. We examine whether early, personal exposure to redlining close to when the maps were drawn is associated with individual level mortality hazard (accelerated failure time) and self-rated health in older adults.

Methods

We used mapped 1940 census enumeration districts to assign 1930s Home Owners' Loan Corporation redlining categories to Health and Retirement Study participants based on 1940 census residence. We ran a survival analysis with a parametric normal distribution MLE to account for survivorship bias, and logistic regression on self-rated health.

Results

1940s redlined D exposure was significantly associated with a 32.7% reduction in expected survival time (95% CI: 2.6%, 53.5%) compared to green A in unadjusted model. Redlined D areas were also associated with 2.26 (95% CI: 1.43, 3.56) the odds of worse self-rated health compared to green A areas.

Discussion

1940 census exposure to 1930s redlining is associated with increased hazards of death and decreased self-rated health in older adults between 1992 and 2018.

Introduction

Early life residential experiences—including exposures to substandard housing and impoverished neighborhoods^{1–4}—have been shown to have strong associations with later life health outcomes and disparities across the life course^{3–5}. These associations are driven by multiple overlapping place-based socio-economic and environmental factors². Place-based factors persist over generations⁶ and are theorized to be caused through policies that entrench and retrench social and political hierarchies^{2,6,7}—such as structural racism—including through redlining^{8–10}.

Areas “redlined” by the Home Owners’ Loan Corporation (HOLC) in the 1930s were drawn to broadly exclude predominantly Black neighborhoods from economic life^{10,11} and are still associated with worse socioeconomic outcomes in the present day^{5,12–14}. The redlining maps therefore serve as a proxy (and possibly cause) for a matrix of ongoing residential segregation policies throughout the 20th century^{10,14,15}.

Substantial scholarship has examined associations between 1930s redlining and present-day health outcomes⁶ at the area level (such as census tract) including cancer incidence and mortality, asthma severity, preterm birth, COVID-19 incidence, firearm mortality, and mortality including age-specific mortality and increased mortality in older age groups^{3,13,16–26}. However, these previous area estimates of health effects associated with redlining may poorly capture the full impact of initial conditions from redlining on individuals²⁴ and may also suffer from ecological fallacy and construct validity issues²⁷.

A few studies have tracked individual rather than area level outcomes^{8,9,28}, but almost all of those^{8,9} used present-day redlining exposure. Of the studies that tracked individual outcomes, only Linde and Egede have examined personal historical exposure to redlining to find increased mortality between 1988 and 2005 among those who lived in redlined areas in the 1940s²⁸. That study, however, used only a subset of US cities²⁸ where 1940 Census enumeration districts could be mapped with a particular method²⁹, and as a result covered only 44% of the US 1940 urban population³⁰. Thus, those findings are limited to only that subset of cities. Additionally, the study is limited by their use of only mortality without addressing quality of life, and by their use of continuous HOLC grade measures despite the non-interval nature of HOLC grades^{31,32}. Connecting mortality (while accounting for average mortality selection effect and right censoring) as well as self-rated health outcomes to redlining status close to the 1930s in a larger set of

cities using ordinal HOLC grades could allow us to better examine the role of initial redlining conditions on the health of older adults in the near present.

In this study, we aim to examine whether early, personal exposure to redlining is associated with long-tail mortality and self-rated health outcomes using individual-level data. Using the provided 1940 enumeration district, we merged historical 1930s redlining maps into a subset of respondents in the Health and Retirement Study (HRS) that had been linked to the 1940 Census³³ (the first census after redlining).

Methods

We combined data from multiple historical, geographic, and longitudinal sources to code Health and Retirement Study (HRS) participants from 1992-2018 who were alive in 1940 with the HOLC redlining category of their residence in the 1940 census. We then used age at death and self-rated health at first HRS interview in the RAND longitudinal version of the HRS³⁴ to analyze the association of 1940 redlining residence exposure with health outcomes in later life.

Independent variable: HOLC category

We used the restricted HRS 1940 Census complete count geographic dataset³³ that provided 1940 enumeration district information. The restricted 1940 full count geographic enumeration district level dataset has n=9602 HRS participants who were probabilistically matched to entries in the 1940 full count census version housed by IPUMS USA as described by Warren et al.³³. Highly probable matched individuals and households were coded with their 1940 enumeration district identifier.

Enumeration districts allowed us to geographically link this subset of HRS participants to HOLC categories of each participant's residence in 1940 using our 1940 "virtual" enumeration districts³⁰. We coded these "virtual" enumeration districts with HOLC category³⁰ by predominance after intersecting with the digital HOLC maps as georeferenced by the Mapping Inequality Project¹¹. Our "virtual" enumeration districts were built algorithmically using address clustering³⁰ from the Urban Transition Project's Geographic Reference File³⁵ alongside the Urban Transition Project's city enumeration district shapefiles²⁹. Our method included cities accounting for 84% of the USA's 1940 urban population³⁰.

Dependent variables

The HRS is described in detail elsewhere³⁶. Briefly, HRS recruits US adults over the age of 50 in birth period cohorts and their spouses and oversamples Black participants and participants living in Florida. The study follows the same participants in waves every two years until they become deceased. We used the RAND longitudinal version of the dataset³⁴ that matches participants consistently across waves from 1992 (wave 1) to 2018 (wave 14) and includes most core variables for each wave including self-rated health and age at death. We merged records from the restricted HRS 1940 Census complete count geographic dataset to the HRS RAND longitudinal file.

We operationalized health as survival time (reported as accelerated failure time) and self-rated health. We used age in months at death as our main outcome variable. If a participant was alive at the end of wave 14 in 2018, we used their age in months at the end of the interview as a right censor indicator. Since some census-linked HRS participants are still alive at the end of the study period and right-censored, and to operationalize quality of life, we also used self-rated health. We used self-rated health at the first interview for a consistent measure for all study participants³⁷. In accordance with common practice and the literature on how participants answer self-rated health³⁸, we dichotomized the measure by grouping Excellent with Very Good; and Good, Poor, and Fair.

Covariates

We controlled for race (Black, white, all other), gender (male, female), marital status (married/partnered, never married, divorced/separated, widowed), foreign birth, uninsured status, residential instability, education (GED/less than high school graduate, high school graduate or more), and wealth at the first interview. We operationalized residential instability using the 1940 census question on whether an individual lives in the same house as in 1935. We classified all responses other than living in the same house and unknown as moved. We dichotomized educational attainment into those who graduated high school and those who did not (or who received their GED later). We collapsed net household wealth into 5 ordered categories, with a category including zero and negative net wealth, then wealth quartiles.

Analysis Methods

We conceptualized the relationship of HOLC category exposure in 1940 with age at death in older age as a time-to-event/survival prospective study with left truncation. In this case, the left truncation occurred

because of the lag time between the 1940 census and the start of the HRS. Since HRS is ongoing and a proportion of our sample is still alive, our study is also subject to right-censoring.

We used a parametric normal distribution maximum likelihood estimation regression model to account for both left truncation and right censoring³⁹. Our variable entry time in the HRS (due to staggering both by cohort and by age within each cohort) might suggest a non-parametric product limit estimator³⁹. However, the near certain likelihood that left-truncated “observations” died earlier than the HRS inclusion criteria of age 50 would give us a biased estimator³⁹ because of mortality selection and survivorship bias⁴⁰ particularly given the large racial disparities in life expectancy throughout the 20th century. Since racial discrimination also underpins redlining, it is plausible that many individuals from redlined areas may have died before they met the age-limited inclusion criteria for HRS, and thus those from redlined areas who survived long enough to enroll in HRS may have been especially healthy. If we looked only at the average life expectancy of those individuals we observed in HRS, those living in redlined areas may look as if they lived longer on average because our sample systematically missed all of those who had much shorter lifespans⁴¹. As a result, our analysis would have faced threats to external validity from average mortality selection effect and internal validity from variation in selection. Instead, we used a parametric model since “adult” or non-neonatal age of death is close to normally distributed⁴². Accounting for left truncation in our survival analysis by modeling the shape of the distribution of “adult” death—which would include those who died before eligibility for HRS inclusion—should prevent attenuation of disparities like those found in other studies with older adults⁴¹.

For the survival analysis, we estimated accelerated failure time by HOLC category first in an unadjusted model. In our second model, we included all controls except for residential instability. In our third model, we introduced residential instability alongside the other controls. For self-rated health, we performed a logistic regression of HOLC category on two levels of self-rated health. We ran a second model with a full set of controls including residential instability. We tested statistical significance at the 95% confidence level and report 95% confidence intervals. All statistical analyses were performed using Stata.

The study was determined exempt by the University of Maryland College Park Institutional Review Board and the University of Maryland Baltimore Institutional Review Board.

Results

Our analytic sample consisted of 2974 HRS participants who were matched in the restricted 1940 Census geographic HRS dataset and who lived in a 1940 enumeration district that overlapped with HOLC categorized areas [Table 1]. 2.8% of our sample lived in green A “Best” enumeration districts, 14.3% in blue B “Still Desirable”, 41.6% in yellow C “Definitely Declining”, and 41.3% in red D “Hazardous” neighborhoods.

Table 1: Summary statistics

Variable	Frequency/units	Mean (SD)/Percent
Total HRS RAND sample	42233	
1940 Census Geo HRS sample	9602	
Analytic sample	2974	
Year of birth	year	1925. 6 (10.2)
Age at first interview (in years)	years	68.3 (10.8)
HOLC categories		
A (green)	83	2.79%
B (blue)	425	14.29%
C (yellow)	1,237	41.59%
D (red)	1,228	41.29%
Age at death in months by HOLC category		
A (green)	years	85.4 (10.8)
B (blue)	years	84.8 (8.9)
C (yellow)	years	83.9 (9.3)
D (red)	years	82.9 (9.4)
Total	years	83.7 (9.3)
Died during study period		
Right Censored	890	29.93%
Died	2,084	70.07%
Self rated Health 1st Interview		
Excellent or Very Good	1,359	45.71%
Good, Fair, or Poor	1,614	54.29%
Race		
white	2,672	89.85%
Black/African American	269	9.05%
All other	33	1.11%
Gender		
male	1,364	45.86%
female	1,610	54.14%

Marital Status		
Never Married	119	4.00%
Married/Partnered	1,154	38.80%
Divorced/Separated/Absent	368	12.37%
Widowed	1,333	44.82%
Foreign-born		
US-born	2,884	97.04%
Foreign-born	88	2.96%
1st interview total wealth (\$)	\$	269185 (508324)
1st interview house net value (\$)	\$	453101 (1402610)
Wealth in 5 categories		
Negative or 0	148	4.98%
Q1	519	17.45%
Q2	682	22.93%
Q3	862	28.98%
Q4	763	25.66%
Education		
GED or Less than HS grad	790	26.56%
HS grad or more	2,184	73.44%
Moved last 5 years 1940 census		
Same House	818	27.51%
Has Moved	1,610	54.14%
Unknown	546	18.36%
Insured 1st Interview		
Uninsured	105	3.55%
Insured	2,856	96.45%

HRS: Health and Retirement Study. HOLC: Home Owners' Loan Corporation

For those participants who died, mean age at death was 1,004 months (83.7 years). 45.7% rated their own health at the first interview as Excellent or Very Good, and 54.3% as Good, Fair, or Poor. The ratio between those who rated their health as Excellent or Very Good to those who rated their health as Good, Fair, or Poor reduced step-wise [Table 2] from green A enumeration districts to redlined D enumeration districts.

Table 2: Self-rated health by HOLC grade

HOLC	Excellent/Very Good	Good/Fair/Poor	Ratio
A (green)	51	28	1.82
B (blue)	218	183	1.19
C (yellow)	581	584	0.99

D (red)	508	644	0.79
Total	1,358	1,439	0.94

HOLC: Home Owners' Loan Corporation

Survival analysis

Our base unadjusted survival model found that redlined D enumeration districts were statistically significantly associated with increased accelerated failure time to death when compared to green A areas [Table 3], with a 32.7% reduction in expected survival time (95% CI: 2.6% to 53.5% reduction).

Table 3: Survival analysis: accelerated failure time by HOLC grade

	AFT	95% CI	
Unadjusted model			
HOLC			
A (green)	ref		
B (blue)		12.9	-28.9 41.1
C (yellow)		28.1	-4.0 50.3
D (red)		32.7	2.6 53.5
Adjusted model			
HOLC			
A (green)	ref		
B (blue)		12.2	-23.4 37.4
C (yellow)		21.4	-8.3 43.0
D (red)		21.0	-9.1 42.8
Moved 1935-1940		2.7	-8.6 12.8
Race			
white	ref		
Black		6.7	-14.7 24.0
All other		35.0	-11.7 62.3
Gender			
male	ref		
female		-41.2	-59.0 -25.5
Marital Status			
Married/Partnered	ref		
Never married		-24.0	-64.9 6.7
Divorced/Separated		-3.2	-23.4 13.8
Widowed		-104.8	-133.3 -79.6
Foreign-born		0.2	-46.8 32.1
Total Wealth			
0 or negative	ref		
Q1		-29.3	-73.5 3.5

Q2	-52.6	-103.6	-14.2
Q3	-100.5	-168.0	-50.1
Q4	-151.5	-239.0	-86.4

Education

GED or less than HS	ref			
HS grad		-37.6	-57.5	-20.1
Insured		-47.4	-92.4	-13.0

AFT: accelerated failure time, reported as percent reduction in expected survival time per unit increase.

HOLC: Home Owners' Loan Corporation. Greyscale: statistically significant at 95% confidence level.

When controls are added, no HOLC category was significantly associated with increased accelerated failure time towards death. The top 3 wealth levels were statistically significant controls, as well as gender, being widowed, education, and health insurance status.

In the full model, with all controls and HOLC category, moving in the last 5 years was not statistically significant, and its inclusion in the model did not appreciably change the coefficients or significance of either our main independent variable or covariates and controls.

Self-rated health

For self-rated health, "yellow-lined" C and redlined D enumeration districts were significantly associated with decreased self-rated health [Table 4]. Yellow C was associated with 1.80 increased odds (95% CI: 1.14 to 2.84) of reporting only Good, Fair, or Poor health. Red D was associated with 2.26 increased odds (95% CI: 1.43 to 3.56) of reporting only Good, Fair, or Poor health.

Table 4: Worse self-rated health (dichotomized) at study entry

		Odds Ratio	95% CI	
Unadjusted model				
HOLC				
A (green)	ref			
B (blue)		1.51	0.93	2.45
C (yellow)		1.80	1.14	2.84
D (red)		2.26	1.43	3.56
Adjusted model				
HOLC				
A (green)	ref			
B (blue)		1.41	0.86	2.32
C (yellow)		1.59	1.00	2.55

D (red)		1.70	1.06	2.72
Moved 1935-1940		1.28	1.09	1.49
Race				
white	ref			
Black		1.38	1.01	1.87
All other		1.03	0.49	2.18
Gender				
male	ref			
female		0.80	0.67	0.94
Marital Status				
Married/Partnered	ref			
Never married		1.35	0.90	2.04
Divorced/Separated		1.09	0.84	1.41
Widowed		1.13	0.94	1.36
Foreign-born		1.14	0.71	1.84
Total Wealth				
0 or negative	ref			
Q1		0.86	0.56	1.33
Q2		0.66	0.43	1.01
Q3		0.52	0.34	0.79
Q4		0.37	0.24	0.57
Education				
GED or less than HS	ref			
HS grad		0.42	0.34	0.50
Insured		1.53	1.01	2.32

HOLC: Home Owners' Loan Corporation. Greyscale: statistically significant at 95% confidence level.

When controls are added, redlined D enumeration districts continued to be associated with worsened self-rated health, reporting 1.70 increased odds (1.06 to 2.72) of reporting only Good, Fair or Poor health.

C enumeration districts were no longer significantly associated with worsened self-rated health.

Race, moving in the last 5 years, gender, top 2 categories of wealth, education and insurance were all statistically significant controls in the model.

Discussion

To understand the association of personal experience with redlining in the 1940s with mortality and quality of life in older age, we analyzed survival time and odds of worse self-rated health by HOLC grade of HRS participant residence 1940 enumeration district. We examined the association with individuals

who were exposed shortly after redlined maps were drawn and found that redlined D “hazardous” enumeration districts were associated with both decreased survival time and worse self-rated in older age in our unadjusted models. In the fully adjusted model, redlined enumeration districts were associated with reduced self-rated health. The associations with health outcomes we found are attenuated by race and wealth controls. These results demonstrate that early direct life experiences with structural racism through redlining are associated with health outcomes across the life course and help to inform whether redlining’s associations with area health outcomes are due solely to concentration of impoverished populations or are partly due to exposures over the life course.

Previous work has found that redlined areas are associated at both area^{3,6,13,16–26} and individual levels with worsened health outcomes for present-day residents^{8,9}, including on mortality and life expectancy. We found that these associations exist not just from present-day residents but also those who were residents when these areas were first redlined after the late 1930s. Our findings are also in line with Linde and Egede’s recent finding in a smaller subset of large US cities (covering 44% of the US 1940 urban population) that living in 1940 in a redlined area was associated with early mortality later in life²⁸. We increase the set of cities to include cities covering 84% of the US 1940 urban population and find a similar pattern with reduced quality of life as well. We also treat HOLC grades as ordinal (and non-interval) rather than continuous to better match the non-monotonic sociological distance between HOLC grades.

Early life has been identified as a key period in setting trajectories of health^{3,4,6,8}. Initial early life exposures in housing and neighborhoods may have stronger associations with health for older adults compared to exposures in adulthood due to how they act on childhood development, whether through physical environment—such as lead exposure⁴³—or social environment—such as Adverse Childhood Experiences⁴⁴. Our findings are broadly consistent with such findings that show that earlier in life exposure to the racialized construction of geographic space^{5,16} is associated with worsened health outcomes later in the life course.

Future Directions

Future analysis should examine whether individuals still live in the same HOLC grade as they did in 1940 to explore whether associations found on the individual level are more associated with initial or continued

exposure to areas redlined in the 1930s, and whether present-day area level effects in redlined neighborhoods are more associated with population change or lack of resources and investment. Our method of measuring exposure to redlining could also be used to connect a larger proportion of the 1940 full count census to vital records or other individual level datasets.

Future analyses could utilize individual address level, since we know georeferenced HOLC categories with far greater certainty than we do enumeration districts, and since HOLC categories are non-cartographic with respect to any other cartographic division. Exact address matching would also enable the inclusion of other measures of interest that are strongly associated with health outcomes from a young age. However, due to changes in city geographies²⁹, exact address matches should be used with caution or snapped to an enumeration district before a dataset of georeferenced 1940 addresses is constructed (rather than simulated from present-day addresses).

Much of the antecedent conditions to redlining stretch to the early postbellum or possibly even antebellum period. Areas where new city arrivals lived (many of whom were Black and/or immigrants) often contained the oldest housing stock^{15,35,45}. Additional work could be done to link histories of place²⁵, forced migration, and compulsory labor throughout the 19th and 20th centuries to help us understand the health landscape in the present day.

Policy Implications

The history of redlining policy may create reparative responsibilities for governance. Institutional, local, state, and national governmental policies created a set of ongoing conditions (likely deliberately) through political disenfranchisement that continue to rob segments of the population of the full length and quality of life that they are owed^{10–12,15,43}. Additional investments in both funding specified for formerly redlined areas and residents and for broad-based social investments are also warranted to reverse decades of population-level harms from structural racism¹.

Limitations

Enumeration districts are area constructions that do not align perfectly with the non-cartographic categorization of HOLC areas³⁰. However, enumeration districts do have a much higher resolution due to their smaller size and geographic compactness than larger geographic units such as census tracts or city-

defined neighborhoods, particularly in dense urban areas^{30,46}. Some participants missing HOLC-categorized enumeration districts may have lived in enumeration districts excluded by the precursor Geographic Reference File dataset by population size (smaller incorporated cities)³⁵. However, the HOLC did not draw maps for most smaller cities^{11,12}.

HOLC categorizations are not necessarily a unified sociological construction among different cities/metropolitan areas^{6,11}. As a power hierarchy, the racial power hierarchy in the US is not an internally consistent construct, but rather may vary in its porousness or the saliency of certain “rules” within each local context to maintain that power structure⁴⁷. As such, the decision to mark certain similar areas as red, yellow, blue, or green reflects local racial attitudes and thus varies within the general bounds of American racial policy from city to city^{11,15}. Additionally, local political contexts are likely to determine how resources and investments were allocated to and from politically marginalized communities from 1940 to the present day¹¹. For this study, we treated HOLC categories as if they were consistent across cities, though we ran some follow-up analysis to investigate this assumption. In subsequent runs, we included indicator variables on state and then on city but did not observe meaningful or significant differences in coefficients or confidence bounds for main variables or controls from our main models.

Conclusion

Direct personal experience of living in a redlined area in the 1940s is associated with increased mortality hazard and worsened self-rated health later in life between 1992 and 2018.

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